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D 5.1 Community onboarding cookbook published

Work Package 5: Community engagement, adoption and onboarding

Task 5.4 Mentoring and onboarding new communities

Technical References

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<i>Document</i>	<i>D 5.1 Community onboarding cookbook published</i>
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<i>Task</i>	<i>5.4 Mentoring and onboarding new communities</i>
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* *PU = Public*

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (incl. the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (incl. the Commission Services)

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Executive Summary

The onboarding cookbook is a set of documents describing the creation of the Galaxy communities of practice called Special Interest Groups (SIG). It outlines the necessary steps which shall precede every SIG creation : search for already existing SIGs which match the required profile; clear definition of the future SIG's goals; setup of SIG's administrative bodies and routines; planning of future publications and training. The Cookbook also lists the minimum of prerequisites required before the creation of a new SIG. The goal of these recommendations is to empower the SIG creators to run a Galaxy community. Success stories of already onboarded communities with different levels of maturity are shared, focusing on their experience in using Galaxy and building their SIGs (Milestone 12 - Interim report on the activities of the 3 early adopters and assessment of the take up by their respective communities).

The Community Onboarding Cookbook link:

<https://galaxyproject.org/get-started/new-leads/>